

NPOWER
BALANCING N & P FLOWS

D8.1

Data Management Plan

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The NPower Project

NPower aims to reduce nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) emissions and rebalance nutrient flows across key sectors in Europe. By advancing nutrient recovery technologies, best management practices (BMPs), and governance measures, the project will contribute to more efficient and circular nutrient use, minimising environmental impact while supporting agricultural and industrial sustainability.

Running for four years from January 2025, NPower will:

- Develop an innovative N/P budgeting software model to analyse and optimise nutrient flows across five key emitting sectors.
- Demonstrate 6 nutrient recovery technologies (RT) to produce sustainable fertilisers.
- Promote 20 best management practices to improve nutrient efficiency and reduce emissions.
- Design and implement governance measures to support effective nutrient management policies at local, regional, and EU levels.
- Facilitate knowledge transfer across four Regional Clusters (RCs) in Spain, Belgium, Finland, and Ireland to ensure EU-wide applicability.

Spain will serve as the main demonstration site, implementing recovery technologies, while the other RCs will assess their applicability and potential replication in their respective contexts. Led by a consortium of 25 partners from across Europe, NPower integrates expertise from research, industry, and policy, covering the entire N/P value chain. This collaboration will provide practical, scalable solutions to optimise nutrient cycles and support the EU's sustainability goals.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
APC	Article Processing Charges
BMP	Best Management Practice
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC BY	Creative Commons 'By'
CC BY-NC	Creative Commons 'By' Non-Commercial
CC BY-ND	Creative Commons 'By' No Derivatives
CC BY-SA	Creative Commons 'By' Share Alike
CC0	Creative Commons Zero
CCRI	Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
CERN	Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire

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Acronym	Description
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
JSON	JavaScript Open Notation
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
M	Month
MAT	MultiActor Transition Group
N	Nitrogen
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure Research for Europe
ORE	Open Research Europe
P	Phosphorus
RC	Regional Cluster
REA	European Research Executive Agency
RF	Recovered Fertiliser
RT	Recovery Technology
WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

1. Executive summary

This deliverable D8.1 “Data Management Plan” describes the management of the data collected, generated and processed along the project lifetime.

The data management plan (DMP) provides a summary of data expected from NPOWER. NPOWER results are formed by deliverables, scientific publications, research data and datasets and multimedia material. Most of these data are text and numerical (.docx, .xlsx, .pdf), but there is also a significant amount of images and videos.

The dissemination of results follows the principle ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’. In addition, a certain amount of peer-reviewed scientific publications will be generated and they will be managed according to the open science approach.

NPOWER Consortium will ensure that results are made findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), respecting the restrictions of IPRs and ethics (personal data protection). Scientific publications, their related metadata and research data will be stored in a public trusted repository, adapting to the multidisciplinary character of NPOWER (Zenodo). This repository provides a safe long-term storage and backup of project results.

This deliverable is the first version of the Data Management Plan. However, the DMP is a living document which will be updated along the project according to schedule and when significant changes take place.

2. Introduction

Urban and industrial excess of nutrients, particularly Nitrogen (N) and Phosphorus (P), represents a major environmental challenge across Europe. The NPOWER project addresses this problem in a systemic and circular manner, recognizing that the current nutrient management practices frequently fail to fully recover or valorise these elements, resulting in missed opportunities for circularity and negative impacts on ecosystems. Circular bioeconomy approaches offer innovative pathways to transform nutrient surpluses into valuable resources for the production of high-added-value bio-based solutions. However, their deployment at regional or national scale faces significant technical, economic, legal and administrative barriers.

The NPOWER project delivers a set of supporting tools to overcome these barriers, working across four Regional Clusters (RCs) representative of Southern, Central, Northern and Western Europe. The project brings together 25 partners with complementary expertise in technical research, socio-economic and governance domains, enabling the delivery of a software for N/P budget in the Region of Murcia, the demonstrations of 6 circular N/P recovery technologies: identification & demonstration of 20 Best Management Practices (BMP) and a kit of Innovative Governance Measures. This integrated approach ensures that NPOWER can effectively demonstrate, replicate, and transfer circular nutrient management solutions, contributing to long-term environmental sustainability across Europe.

The objective of the present deliverable is to develop the Data Management Plan (DMP) of NPOWER project. A data management plan describes the data management life cycle for the data. The structure is based on the recommended template in the Guidelines for Horizon Europe Programme projects [1], but trying to adapt to the particular characteristics of NPOWER project, which makes it unique. Data Management Plan is a document that provides the guidelines of how to manage the amount of data collected and generated from NPOWER project. This means a first stage of identification of the data collected, processed and generated in the project (types, datasets, formats) and a description of the measurements done for making the data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. The document also explains the plans for allocation of resources and provisions related to security and ethics. In any case more detailed information about ethics (personal data protection) are developed in deliverable D8.2 “Ethics” (sensitive).

3. Data summary

3.1 Data classification

The generation, collection and management of high-quality data is a crucial part of the success in NPOWER project objectives. Therefore, the access to data of high quality and their processing is essential. Data can be classified according to diverse criteria, as shown in Table 1.

The data will be mainly text, numerical and images, which means that the main formats are .docx, .xlsx and .pdf. However, a relevant amount of multimedia material (images, videos, webinars, podcast, presentations) is generated for communication through the online platforms, social media, etc., using formats such as .jpg, .png, .mp4, .pptx.

Table 1. Data classification according to different criteria

Criteria	Type		Examples
Origin	Primary	Generated by the project	Results from experiments, answers to interviews, reports generated, outcome of meetings.
	Secondary	Already existing from the partners or external sources	Reports, databases, books
Purpose	Inputs	Original data	Questionnaires, bibliography, databases, outcomes from other sources
	Intermediate data	Processed data, but not final	Databases, spreadsheets, preliminary reports
	Outputs	Results of the project	Reports, deliverables, publications, multimedia materials, results of experiments

The characteristics of the project make that the nature of the data generated and treated is very diverse according to the work package (WP), as shown in Table 2. In the case of the pilots of Recovery Technologies (RTs) in WP3, there will be many numerical data from the experiments together with reports and graphics.

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Numerical outcomes are also expected from the evaluation and demonstration tests of the recovered fertilisers (RFs). From this side it is expected a typical research data generation. However, the fact that the reports about the demonstration of RTs are sensitive in order to protect the IPRs of the technology developers, makes that the management of the data coming from WP3 need to be treated with care.

A different situation takes place for those WPs connected to the Regional Clusters (RCs) and Multiaction Transition Groups (MATs). In those cases, the primary data expected are the results of the meetings and communication with stakeholders. They will be text data in most cases with some numerical information. As in many cases the purpose of the meetings is data collection, many of them will not be newly generated, but reused from other sources internal or external to the Consortium according to the stakeholder in the corresponding RC or MAT providing the data. Data coming from the RCs are expected to be purely in form of text regarding WP5 about governance. In the particular case of WP4, a ratio between text data as description of the best management practices (BMPs) and numerical information coming from the demonstration of the BMPs by UPCT is expected. The processing of the data generated and obtained can provide material for dissemination.

Table 2. Identification of data from NPOWER project

WP	Description	Type	Expected formats
WP1	Outcomes from MAT first meetings (minutes, Miro boards)	Text, image	.docx, .png, .jpg, .pdf
WP2	Budget reports	Text	.docx, .pdf
WP2	Datasets underlying the budget	Numeric, databases	.xlsx
WP3	Research data from RT pilots, Reports from RT pilots Reports from RF	Numeric, text, graphs	.docx, .xlsx, .pdf
WP3	Research data from evaluation RFs. Reports.	Numeric, text, graphs	.docx, .xlsx, .pdf
WP3	Research data from demonstration of RFs. Reports.	Numeric, text, graphs	.docx, .xlsx, .pdf

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WP	Description	Type	Expected formats
WP4	Outcomes from the MATs Public deliverables Datasets underlying the BMP demonstration	Numeric, text, graphs	.docx, .png, .jpg, .pdf, .xlsx
WP5	Outcomes from the RC meetings and workshops Reports	Text, image	.docx, .png, .jpg, .pdf
WP6	Environmental LCA + underlying datasets	Numerical, databases	.xlsx, .pdf
WP6	Economic assessment + underlying dataset	Numerical, databases	.xlsx, .pdf
WP6	Social assessment, surveys, underlying datasets	Text, numerical, databases	.docx, .xlsx, .pdf
WP7	Communication materials (videos, podcast, factsheets)	Text, video, audio	.pdf, .mp4, .docx,

There are two WPs in which data are the core matter. These are WP2, regarding the budget of nitrogen and phosphorus in the Region of Murcia and WP6, regarding the evaluation in environmental, economic and social terms of the solutions proposed in NPOWER. In these cases, the classification indicated in Table 1 about the purpose is much clearer. The type of data expected are mainly numerical, databases, text and models. For performing the assessments, it is essential to have a large amount of numerical raw data. In the case WP2 many of these data are coming from bibliography, official statistics or either direct communication with stakeholders through the MATs. These data require treatment in many cases in order to adapt to the purpose of the budget. This will also generate a new dataset of curated data. Finally, the application of the model will give the final results, expected also to be numerical.

In the case of the environmental, economic and social assessments the primary data will come both from the outcomes of NPOWER, especially from the pilots and demonstration of the BMPs and from the scientific publications and reports.

In addition to data mentioned, NPOWER project requires the identification of actual or potential entities, organizations, or persons in relation with RCs and MATs considering their relevant roles as stakeholders. Databases of external stakeholders will be created for the constitution and consolidation of the MATs.

These databases will include only the necessary personal data or data publicly available from corporate websites. The databases do not have very large size. Therefore, the text data or numerical are collected in spreadsheets (.xlsx) or text lists (.docx, .pdf).

In addition, databases are generated for the events scheduled by NPOWER project (General Assembly meetings, RC meetings). The management of the lists and their data is done according to General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

3.2 Results

The project NPOWER will generate results from different nature based on the data summarised in the previous section. It is important to establish a difference between the results themselves and the research data, as in most cases the latter are not the final result. According to REA, research data is the information (facts or numbers) collected to be examined and considered, and to serve as basis for reasoning, discussion or calculation [2]. Results can have different nature (reports, datasets, scientific publications).

Results will be obtained in project NPOWER in form of the scheduled deliverables, both public and sensitive and actions of dissemination. It is important to determine how the results will be managed, which is explained in more detail in deliverable D7.2 “Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan”, including the degree and form of dissemination or exploitation. In the case of deliverable reports, most are public and 10 are categorized as sensitive, which means that they must keep confidentiality according to the provisions in Article 13 of Grant Agreement. Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) need also to be considered. As a general principle, the Consortium follows the European Commission (EC) recommendations on open data and it is “as open as possible, and as closed as necessary” to protect the associated exploitation rights when required. This means that results and data may be kept closed if making them public is against the researcher’s legitimate interests or if personal data are involved. Sensitive data, data subject to IPR and personal data are treated according to the Grant Agreement and to the relevant legal framework.

Specific rules on dissemination of Grant Agreement (Art.17.4) establishes a protocol where any beneficiary intending to disseminate their results, must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of at least 15 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate. Any other beneficiary may object within 15 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests (Art 17).

Reports

Reports are the main results of NPOWER project, mainly in the form of deliverables and Practical Abstracts, besides other reports which might not fall within any of those categories. Deliverables include outcomes from the research and from the co-creation in the RCs and MATs. It is clearly stated in the Description of the Action in NPOWER Grant Agreement which deliverables are sensitive and which ones are public. These public deliverables will be accessible to the public through the project website and may be used also by the Commission and the Agency for communication and publicizing activities. Some public deliverables will be also available in the website or platforms from the [Circular Cities and Regions Initiative \(CCRI\)](#). Sensitive reports with high dissemination and communication interest can be adapted in order to generate public versions by removal of sensitive information, as far as the legitimate interest is safeguarded.

The final versions of reports are normally text data (.docx, .pdf), but might also include images and diagrams (.jpeg, .png).

Scientific publications

Due to its technical nature, NPOWER project will generate results for dissemination to the scientific community. These publications are regulated by Article 17 in the Grant Agreement and are part of the dissemination strategy. The objectives of NPOWER project in terms of scientific publications is explained in the D7.2 “Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan”. The project should disseminate results. The dissemination of results should respect the obligations regarding IPRs (Art 16), confidentiality and security (Art 13) and data protection (Art 15).

The kind of scientific publications include:

- Peer-reviewed publications in scientific journals. This is the most important means of dissemination in the scientific community. It is based on journals where the publication is subject to the revision and approval by other relevant experts in the scientific area. The journals have normally an indexing and impact factors. The higher the impact factor, the higher number of persons it arrives.
- Non peer-reviewed publications in scientific or technical journals. This kind of publications are normally based on technical journals, but the publication does not need a previous process of revision and approval by peers. They might also have an indexing but normally the impact factor is low. In general, they have a national scope.
- Contributions to scientific conferences (oral presentations, conference proceedings, poster, etc.). National and international thematic events are organised to present the latest advances in specific scientific areas. These are

normally events to present the latest research results. In general, the impact of conference participations is lower than those in scientific publications, but they are also considered an important means for results dissemination. The kind of participation is normally either as oral presentations or by the presentation of posters in dedicated poster sessions. The conferences release normally a book of abstracts, which is also considered a scientific publication. In some cases, extended abstracts are requested which may take the form of a small article.

- Other scientific publications in any medium.

The final publishable versions of scientific publications are normally text data (.docx, .xlsx, .pdf), but might also include images and diagrams. In the case of conferences, in addition to the text data (for the proceedings and books of abstracts) in typical text formats (.docx, .pdf), there might be also presentations (.pptx), images (.jpg, .png) and videos (.mp4).

In addition to scientific journals, it is also considered the publication in the platform Open Research Europe (ORE). This platform is oriented to research coming from Horizon Europe projects and is peer-reviewed. The peer-review process is open and it consists first in the publication of a first version of the article within ten days of submission. Then, expert reviewers are selected and invited, and their reviews and names are published alongside the article together with the authors' responses and comments from registered users. Once the articles pass the peer review they are sent to major indexing databases and repositories. The platform Open Research Europe was launched formally on March 2021 [3].

The scientific publications are normally the result of processing research data, which means that articles might display one part of the original data or the processed data. The publications have tables, graphs, numbers which might require the availability of those research data to validate the results. In many cases the amount of research data makes unfeasible its publication in the article. In such case the research data needed to validate the results are known as underlying data.

Metadata

Metadata are a set of data associated to publications or any other material which allow its characterization by providing basic information such as title, authors, affiliation, abstract, etc. Metadata are useful for making the data findable for scholars and for their classification. Depending on the discipline, there are different standards of metadata, which provide different sets of information [4], [5]. Publishers (journals) have normally their own standard of metadata, although there are several international standards widely used among the scientific community such as the JavaScript Open Notation (JSON) Schema, Data Cite Schema, BibTeX, Extensible Markup Language (XML) or Dublin Core.

According to Grant Agreement Art. 17.4 specific rules, the metadata from the publications generated in NPOWER must be in a standard format and include the following information:

- Description
- Date of deposit
- Authors
- Embargo
- Horizon Europe funding
- Grant project name, acronym and number (balancing Nitrogen and Phosphorus flows by budgeting at Regional scale, NPOWER, GA number 101181873)
- Licensing terms
- Persistent identifiers for the dataset (for instance DOI)
- Where applicable persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs

These concepts will be developed in more detail in section FAIR of *4. Open Science Plan*. All the deliverables of NPOWER include information in the “Document Information” section at the beginning of the document.

Multimedia materials

In this category it can be included material in form of videos, podcasts, webinars, images, graphs used for dissemination and communication through different channels. The most relevant materials generated are hosted in the website and showcased also on Youtube and social media sites (i.e. LinkedIn). The most suitable formats are selected on a case by case basis in agreement with the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan. These materials are expected to have variable size depending on their duration and their degree of resolution.

Some of Consortium meetings will be held online (i.e. Microsoft Teams, Zoom) and recorded in video giving files with important size. Several important meetings (some MATs, hybrid General Assembly or Executive Board meetings) will be held online, which means an important amount of data (video) with large size. In any case, these recordings are kept as sensitive in most cases.

4. Open Science Plan

As part of the program Horizon Europe, NPOWER project needs to comply with the principles of open science. This approach is based on cooperation and sharing of knowledge, results and tools as early and widely as possible. Open science is led by the Project Coordinator (CETENMA), within the framework of Task 8.3 “Data management and ethics”. It comprises of the measures to make the data findable,

accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), and the policy for open science both internally (within the Consortium) and externally (with other projects or initiatives).

3.3 FAIR Data

Findable

4.1.1 Persistent Identifiers

Scientific publications are generally identified by a persistent identifier such as Digital Object Identifier (DOI). This number, which has normally a link associated allows the classification and indexing of any material. These persistent identifiers, are generated by the publisher for scientific journals [6], especially for those peer-reviewed. Some open access repositories, provide also their own DOI since the moment of uploading the data [7]. Therefore, it might happen that for some publications stored also in repositories there are available 2 DOI (one from publisher and one from repository). This number of DOI might increase if there are several versions of the same publication.

Scientific publications, public reports, Practical Abstracts, factsheets, good practices and other research data (underlying data) and materials uploaded to repository (see Accessible section) will have their own DOI. It is highly recommendable to provide also a persistent identifier for materials uploaded in the website.

The partners should make sure that the abstracts and materials sent and presented in scientific conferences get their own persistent identifier.

4.1.2 Naming

Data must be easy to find internally according to the internal open science principles. It is recommendable that the name of the file provides enough information to identify its content. Due to the multidisciplinary of the project, standard naming systems might be implemented within each WP, so that requirements for their functionality can be fulfilled. In general, the naming might include information such as: name of the project (NPOWER), WP, Task (in case the name is not descriptive enough), description of the file, RC, MAT or RT (if applicable), Date (specifying date, month and year), version number (if applicable), Draft (if applicable) and deliverable number (if applicable).

Accessible

The results from NPOWER project follow the rule “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”, considering the exceptions mentioned for data subject to intellectual property rights (IPRs), mainly from WP3, (although WP2 and WP4 might

potentially face similar situation). The results, public deliverables and research data need to be openly accessible, which is ensured by several ways:

- NPOWER Website
- Open access routes for publications
- Public repositories
- Websites of other EU initiatives or projects

All the research data will have long-term validity and will be documented and be available after 5 years

The deliverables classified as sensitive (only for the members in the Consortium and the European Commission) will remain sensitive unless the provisions indicated in the Grant Agreement (Art.13.1) and Consortium Agreement (Section 10) are fulfilled. Besides the confidentiality, the classification of the data restricted to public are decided on a case by case basis, taking into account Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), protection of personal data, legitimate interests of the partners and other criteria to be further described in the dissemination and exploitation plan (D7.1).

4.1.3 Public repository

Horizon Europe is included in OpenAIRE platform, this means that the results generated in the project must be made accessible by the use of an open access trusted repository. This means a publicly maintained, long-term repository providing access without any user account or password.

According to Article 17 of Grant Agreement, a machine-readable copy of the scientific publications or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication must be deposited in a repository for scientific publications as soon as possible, not later than its time of publication. Previous versions of the publication might be stored previously in the repository. Associated metadata in standard format need also to be stored in an open access trusted repository.

As part of Open Science, in addition to the scientific publications, the following research data will be uploaded in a public repository and made accessible:

- All research data needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, including the metadata that describe the research data deposited (underlying data). These data must be deposited as soon as possible and at the latest on publication.
- Information about the tools needed to validate the results.

Research data of the publications should be stored in the same repository as the publication.

Public deliverables will be uploaded to the trusted repository as soon as possible and at latest 30 days after their submission. Datasets associated to public

deliverables will also be stored in the repository as soon as possible and at latest 30 days after the public deliverable submission.

NPOWER Partners will use a trusted repository, connected to the tools proposed by the European Commission, including the information requested by the EC. OpenAIRE tools allow finding a suitable certified repository for granting open access to different outcomes (publications, data) from a long list of potential repositories related with different disciplines [8]. However, in case that the topic of search does not match with any of the repositories in the list, OpenAIRE recommends the use of Zenodo. Zenodo is an open access repository operated by CERN [9]. Data are stored in the same cloud infrastructure as CERN's Large Hadron Collider and using the repository software Invenio [7].

NPOWER project generates publications in very different areas of knowledge. This means that although there are journals and repositories suitable for some of the data, there are other publications and data not fitting into them. From a practical point of view, and considering that this Data Management Plan is a dynamic document, it is recommended the use of Zenodo as standard repository.

In addition, public data will be published in the European Open Science Cloud EU Node once the services and use of this platform are more clearly defined [10]. The EOSC EU Node is a platform for research knowledge sharing which is a key element on the EU Open Science Policy.

Other materials from NPOWER project such as videos, podcast, webinar recordings, public deliverables, public reports, etc., are in general accessible to users of the website. Besides the accessibility to these contents through the website, it might be recommendable to upload into a public repository in order to ensure its integrity beyond the lifetime of NPOWER.

Regarding the rest of the materials, their distribution is decided on a case-by-case basis.

4.1.4 Open access publication routes

According to Article 17 of Grant Agreement, and as part of Horizon Europe Program, NPOWER Project has the obligation to make the peer-reviewed scientific publications openly available or Open Access. Open access means free of charge online access for any user. The files can not only be read online, downloaded and printed, but also copied, distributed, searched, linked, crawled and mined [11][12].

There are 3 main routes to open access [11][12]. Each partner will choose the most suitable route to peer-reviewed scientific publications arising from the project.

- Green open access. The author or a representant deposits the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript in and online repository before, at the same time, or after the publication. The publication is free of

charge for the author, but some publishers request that the open access be granted only after a period of time (embargo).

- Golden open access. The article is published immediately in open access mode. The most common business model is that the Article Processing Charges (APC) are paid by authors.
- Open Research Europe. The article is published immediately in open access mode. The peer-review process starts after publication and it is publicly available. The publication is free of charge for the author, as the platform is intended for European-funded projects.

In general, the Open Research Europe route will be preferred, considering that the publication is immediate, free of charge for EU projects and it provides automatically a DOI and metadata. However, if it is estimated that a higher impact can be obtained through the publication in other scientific journals, the publisher will be chosen amongst those who respect both the authors' interests and accept the terms of open access publication. The selection of the journal will be in agreement with the Dissemination Exploitation and Communication Plan (D7.1) and it will take in consideration the available resources if golden open access is required.

Interoperable

Due to the multidisciplinary nature of NPOWER, it is essential to standardise concepts. All the data will be of coherent file formats, unified vocabularies and references, following the guidelines of the targeted trusted repositories. As general approach, the common definition of concepts based on EU legislations is preferred. In case of ambiguity, standardized vocabularies might be used. If necessary, instructions and explanations (i.e. Readme files) are provided to allow interoperability. This approach has been used in several tasks.

Formats such as .docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .pptx and different common image (.jpg, .png) and video (.mp4) compatible with Microsoft Office 365 is unavoidably required, the suitable provisions should be taken to ensure interoperability.

English is the official language in NPOWER project documentation and the preferred vehicle of communication between partners from different languages. In case that the use of a language different than English is required, it must be ensured when necessary that the information is accurately translated or transposed (i.e. meetings of RCs, capacity-building workshops) from the local languages to English and viceversa. In a similar way, a proper English summary must be provided in case of publications in a language different than English, in order to ensure the interoperability.

Reusable

The public deliverables can be used by the European Commission in agreement with Article 16.3 of Grant agreement about “Rights of use of the granting authority on materials, documents and information received for policy, information, communication, dissemination and publicity purposes”.

Reusability of the data is ensured by the licensing. In this sense the licenses of Creative Commons (CC) are widely spread. Among them the most widely spread in the scientific community are [13], [14]:

- CC BY. This license allows reusers to distribute, remix, adapt and build upon the material in any medium or format, so long as attribution is given to the creator. It allows commercial use.
- CC 0 (CC Zero). This is a public dedication tool, which allows creators to waive their copyright and put their works into the worldwide public domain. CC0 allows reusers to distribute, remix, adapt and build upon the material in any medium or format with no conditions.

It must be stated that within the group of CC BY there are different versions, some of which only allow non-commercial use (CC BY-NC), some which oblige the adaptations and changes to be shared under the same terms (CC BY-SA) and other which does not allow modifications (CC BY-ND), and combinations of them.

In their decision from 22nd February 2019 the European Commission adopted Creative Commons as open license under the European Commission reuse policy [15]:

1. Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Public License (CC BY 4.0) is adopted as an open license for the Commission’s reuse policy under Article 6 of Decision 2011/833/EU
2. Without prejudice to the preceding article, raw data, metadata or other documents of comparable nature may alternatively be distributed under the provisions of the Creative Commons Universal Public Domain Dedication deed (CC0 1.0)

This is implemented in Art. 17 of the Grant Agreement, being adapted to the latest version of CC BY or a licence with equivalent rights for scientific publications, reports and deliverables. In the case of metadata, they must be under public domain license CC0 or equivalent.

In the particular case of long-text formats and monographs, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works by the use of CC BY-NC and/or CC BY-ND.

3.4 Internal open science

The same concept of open science is ensured within the Consortium by creating collaborations between partners and synergies.

Data availability is ensured for the correct implementation of the action, including the different assessments to be performed in WP6. In this case, the measures regarding the rights of access for the implementation of the action established in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement will be followed.

Results, documents, research data and any other data are stored in an internal secured repository (sharepoint) from the Consortium. This common repository is based on Microsoft Office 365 (OneDrive) and it is administrated by the Project Coordinator (CETENMA), granting the access for the members in the Consortium.

In this sense, the Project Coordinator is uploading the final version of the deliverables to the sharepoint when submitted, as well as keeping the track of minutes and updating the mailing list. The sharepoint is active along the lifetime of the project and 5 years after the end of the project.

The concept of interoperability mentioned in the section Interoperable are applicable internally. Formats in text or numerical (.docx, .xlsx, .pptx) will be included in addition to .pdf to ensure the internal interoperability of templates and presentations.

If needed, Readme files will be created to ensure the reusability of the generated data.

3.5 External open science

The concept of external open science is applicable to the connection of NPOWER project with other projects and EU initiatives in order to will create an innovation ecosystem, avoid duplicities, and maximize EU efforts.

In a first level of collaboration, NPOWER is establishing synergies with the sister projects of the same topic: GREENHOOD (<https://greenhoodproject.eu/>) and AQUAPHOENIX (<https://aquaphoenix.eu/>). These two projects share the same topics in different areas, but there are data of applicability in the three sister projects so that NPOWER can benefit from the open science approach, as well as GREENHOOD and AQUAPHOENIX.

Regarding initiatives, NPOWER is part of the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) and it is also connected to the Horizon Europe Mission on Oceans and Waters. Interactions will include the publication of public deliverables and scientific publications in their corresponding websites, ensuring that NPOWER results arrive to a larger audience.

All this collaboration will be done in agreement with the requirements regarding IPRs and personal data protection.

This coordinated engagement will enhance the consistency of messages, promote knowledge exchange, and position NPOWER within the broader ecosystem of zero-pollution and circular economy initiatives at the European level.

5 Allocation of resources

The project has ensured the necessary resources for proper data management and open science. Firstly, all the partners have PM available in WP7 and WP8 for dissemination, communication, exploitation and data management in order to ensure that the project results are disseminated.

CETENMA, as Project Coordinator has allocated resources for the maintenance of the internal sharepoint and for providing access through trusted repositories.

In terms of the publication in scientific journals, Open Research Europe fulfils the requirements of open access dissemination, as it is free of charge for the project. In the particular case of golden open access, the partners need to make use of budget as Other Goods and Services for paying the Article Processing Fees. The same is applicable to part of the budget for the presentation of the results in scientific conferences and events, but they need to provide open access for being eligible costs.

6 Data security

Data security is intended here mainly from two perspectives: i) ensure that data are not lost in case of malfunction of hardware or software and ii) protection of sensitive data (under IPR or GDPR). Therefore, a system for backup of all the project information is required. In addition, measurements should be taken in order to avoid piracy or the release of sensitive information either personal data or confidential data. In the case of website, security measurements (i.e. firewalls, passwords, encryption) are employed when handling personal and/or sensitive data. NPOWER complies with GDPR. The provisions necessary to ensure data security are applied both for internal and external communication.

Backup

The strategies of accessibility of the data provided previously (Making data publicly accessible) ensures the backup of data in case of problems with personal computers. Therefore, backup is provided by means of the use of public repositories such as Zenodo, which is supported by CERN and has both the

commitment to collect and store data and maintain them in over the next 20 years. In the highly unlikely event that Zenodo will have to close operations, it is guaranteed that all the contents will be migrated into suitable repositories. No link or citation will be affected, as all the material in Zenodo has DOI. [16], [17]. Backup is also provided by the websites of the publishers in case of publications.

The security and backup of NPOWER data is ensured also by the use of the internal repositories mainly based on Microsoft Office 365 One Drive and Microsoft Teams. The use of the common sharepoint administrated by the Coordinator and the WP-specific repositories ensures that all data files are kept for NPOWER Consortium use despite problems in personal computers. In addition to this, each partner will take appropriate technical and organization measures against accidental loss or destruction of project data.

Internal accessibility

Project documentation is stored and exchanged through the use of a private, password protected secure and confidential platform administered by the Project Coordinator. NPOWER Microsoft Office 365 One Drive, where there is information of all the WPs, is only accessible by project partners upon the provision of user name and password. The Coordinator administrates access to this sharepoint. In case of use of the platform Microsoft Office OneDrive, protection against viruses and data piracy is granted [18]. Security of internal mailing communication between Consortium is also considered. In addition, each partner will take appropriate technical and organizational measures against information breach.

7 Ethics

All activities developed and implemented within NPOWER comply with fundamental ethical principles including those reflected in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (2000/c 364/01) and the code of ethics of the individual institutions that are involved in the consortium. NPOWER activities also reflect and comply with individual institutions' codes of conduct for research, stakeholder engagement activities and guidelines.

Personal data

7.1.1 Technical and organisational measures

These measures safeguard the rights and freedom of data subjects and research participants and prevent unauthorized access to personal data. NPOWER project will fully comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2016/679

and Directive 2002/58/EC. In addition, each partner will take appropriate technical and organizational measures to ensure personal data protection.

Data minimisation

The personal data to be collected and processed will be minimal, relevant and limited to the purposes of the project, both from the point of view of communication, registration and for research activities. This principle of minimisation does not only apply to collection, but also to the extent to which they may be accessed, further processed and/or shared, the purposes for which they are used, and the period for which they are kept.

The organisers of events will make sure that only the necessary data are required, which means mainly name, email address and organisation. The information regarding personal data will be under the charge of the event organizer. Consent forms will be placed to disposal of the participants in case that they would like to engage with the rest within the framework of the events. In RCs it will be required only the least information possible to draw a general profile of the participants to collectively co-create knowledge.

In the case of website, only the data required for contact in the newsletter and communication are collected.

General measures

This Section summarises the general provisions that will be considered to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subjects and prevent unauthorised access to personal data. These principles have as a reference the EU legislation about data protection (GDPR) and the mandate from Article 39.2 of the grant agreement. They constitute the NPOWER principles for data protection, which come as follows:

- Prior to personal data collection the necessary notifications and/or authorisations for collecting and processing the data and the free and fully informed consent of the persons concerned (data subjects) will be obtained.
- No collection of personal data on a citizen or any other stakeholder without permission. Informed consent will be obtained from any participant in RC activities with the provision of online or physical forms supported by the necessary information for the individual to make a voluntary informed decision about whether or not to participate in any session.
- The consent request shall be clear, concise and unambiguous, using language that is easy to understand and clearly distinguishable from other pieces of information (Article 4(11) GDPR [19]).
- The consent request has to specify what use will be made of the personal data and include contact details of the company processing the data

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- Individuals whose personal data is being processed shall be treated fairly and in an open and transparent manner.
- No sensitive data such as health, sexual lifestyle, ethnicity, political opinion, religious or philosophical conviction will be collected
- Regardless of the approach or channel being used for personal data collection and processing (online or offline), it is highly recommended to prepare and communicate the GDPR compliant privacy (and cookie policy where applicable) to the data subjects.
- Personal data information will only be used for the purposes covered by agreement, and will not be retained except as required for these purposes
- Personal data shall be accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date. Where Personal Data are found to be inaccurate or incomplete, having regard to the purposes for which they are processed, they shall be rectified or deleted.
- The individuals whose personal data is being collected and processed have the right to:
 - i) obtain a copy of their Personal Data being stored by the NPOWER partner without undue delay;
 - ii) request that any Personal Data relating to them which is shown to be incomplete or inaccurate be rectified
 - iii) request that on compelling legitimate grounds processing of their Personal Data should cease
 - iv) know the contact details of the Project Coordinator and/or DPO to which the individual should direct requests in relation to their rights above.
- Images or videos of the data subjects where they are clearly identified shall not be used without consent
- Personal data will be stored securely during project duration, and provisions will be made to ensure that the data will be secured safely beyond the lifetime of this project when applicable
- Personal data information collected in this project will be kept confidential and never become public, findable or accessible, unless proper measures for anonymization are taken or consent provided
- The access to personal data will be done only by authorised personnel which will follow the measures and norms described by their organisations regarding data protection according to GDPR and the general principles of the project
- Files or documents with personal data will be only accessible by project partner upon the provision of user name and personal password, when stored electronically (i.e. with Microsoft Office 365 OneDrive or Microsoft Teams). In case the personal data are physical format, proper measures must be taken to ensure the access only to the authorised personnel (i.e. locked cabinets)
- Personnel will only access those personal data resources required for the correct development of the tasks in the project. The person responsible for

D8.1 Data Management Plan

the file will use pre-established mechanisms to prevent other users from accessing.

- When applicable, personal data will be stored in safe and suitable repositories, such as Microsoft Office 365 (One Drive) and Microsoft Teams in order to avoid any accidental loss or erasure due to technical problems in personal computers.
- Appropriate technical and organization measures shall be taken against accidental loss or destruction of, or damage to, personal data information.
- Processing of personal data shall comply with applicable EU and national law on data protection (including authorisations or notification requirements).
- Processing of personal data shall be adequate, relevant and not excessive in relation to the purposes for which they are processed.
- Personal data shall never be transferred to individuals or organisations outside NPOWER Consortium unless there is an appropriately enforced legal request.
- Personal data shall be retained until they are used, and destroyed after the finalisation of NPOWER according to the applicable EU regulations, policies on record retention and data disposal, and any other applicable guidelines, depending on the purpose for what they were collected and processed
- Collected personal data used for research will be stored and processed electronically in servers located within the European territory.
- The partner obtaining the data shall not disclose personal data unless in accordance with these principles of personal data processing.
- The personal data collected will be kept within the Consortium without making it available to any third party or external body. In principle, the personal data should be shared only by those Consortium partners who need them for the correct development of their tasks
- Information will not be made public or provided to third parties without explicit permission
- Contractual and technical controls will be applied to prevent information becoming inadvertently available to third parties.
- Individuals can report suspected breaches of this principles to NPOWER Project Coordinator and/or DPO
- Any NPOWER partner shall respond to suspected breaches of Personal Data Protection established under these principles promptly and effectively and take the appropriate action where a breach is found to have occurred. The Project Coordinator will manage this issue following the Consortium Agreement.
- In the cases of contracts with external companies to process personal data, the contract for the provision of services will include specific obligations for privacy, confidentiality and compliance with personal data protection regulations. Such companies are required to provide copies of their data protection security documents, certifications and accreditations obtained and audits carried out to comply with legal requirements.

Any personal data electronically collected and mined will be anonymised to prevent the identification of individual subjects unless informed consent is granted.

- In the website:
 - Mention to the visitor the use of cookies (if applicable) and inform about cookies policy
 - Ask consent to visitors prior to the submission of personal information, making the privacy policy available at that time in line with GDPR regulations.
 - Keeping third-party data processors to a minimum. In case of using third-party data processors, use only those with industry standard privacy measures
- As general rule, no profiling or tracking of personal data should be done unless necessary for the purposes of the project. In case cookies are used, the user shall be informed and consent must be requested.

Anonymisation

Strategies for protection of sensitive data might include anonymization and pseudonymization. Anonymization is an irreversible procedure after which the data subject cannot be identifiable by the data anymore [21]. Anonymization will be used when possible when the identity of the person is not relevant for the purposes of the task. This might be obtained by means of substitution of the name with a numerical identifier. Zenodo gives the responsibility to the data uploaders to ensure that the sensitive personal data are either anonymized to an appropriate degree or fully consent cleared.

7.1.2 Informed consent

Data collection and treatment is performed following ethical principles and informed consent. Personal data collection is required in some of the WPs for events organization or for RCs and MATs consolidation and management. These personal data, mainly professional, consist on names, e-mail addresses and organization. Sensitive details (food allergies) are collected only when strictly necessary and kept as confidential as possible. Contact with the potential Members-to-be of the MATs is done according to GDPR. The same approach is applied for registered users in website. Consent forms are provided for the users registered to ask whether they agree with the terms. Data regarding website will not be used by them for any purpose, unless user consents (i.e. receive informative e-mail).

The activities in events such as the Regional Clusters, MATs and capacity building workshops involve the participation of humans. The outcomes of these activities are results of the project, being made public in most cases in form of reports, although they might generate scientific publications. The procedures and criteria for the recruitment in these activities is established according with ethics

standards, ensuring equity and clarity, following the ethical guidelines established by the Ethics responsible KVC in deliverable D8.2 “Ethics”.

Priority is given to asking and obtaining the participants’ signed forms of free, voluntary and informed consent and only in case where signing consent may put in danger their anonymity there will be an oral consent attentively asked for and taken from the participants. An example of consent form is found in *10. Annex*. The specific informed consent form for the participation in the RC and MAT meetings will be found in D1.2 “MATs methodology”. Besides the aspects related to personal data protection, these forms should explain that the outcomes of their participation in events might provide results for dissemination, although the reports or eventual scientific publications are not expected to involve personal data. In principle, it is not foreseen the participation of children and minors. Further information can be found in Deliverable D8.2 Ethics.

Confidentiality

The management of sensitive data will follow what established in Article 13 of Grant Agreement and its specific rules, as well as the Section 10 of Consortium Agreement. These data, documents or materials are marked as “sensitive information” by writing. It is not expected that classified information is involved in the implementation of NPOWER.

In addition, each partner will take appropriate technical and organizational measures to ensure sensitive data protection. When the task involves the management of sensitive data measurements will be required to avoid information breach, especially for those activities where the participation of external stakeholders is required. If necessary, the procedures for recruitment of external stakeholders for the RC members might include provisions for confidentiality when required, such as the signature of a non-disclosure agreement (NDA).

Besides the provisions for personal and sensitive data, as established by the Grant Agreement in Article 17.4 specific rules, any partner intending to disseminate their results, must give advance notice to the other partners of at least 15 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate. In this way it is assured that every partner revise whether sensitive information is being published. The other partners have 15 days to object in case their legitimate interests would be significantly harmed. Appropriate measures will also be taken in case of materials uploaded to website.

8 Conclusions

The NPOWER project, as a multidisciplinary initiative addressing the complex challenge of balancing nitrogen and phosphorus flows at regional scale, will collect, process and generate diverse results and research data for its successful implementation. This deliverable develops the data management plan of NPOWER project. They have been identified and classified the different data of the project. They are mainly in format text and numerical (.docx, .pdf, .xlsx), but multimedia materials (videos, podcast, webinars, presentations) are also generated. Datasets will be generated for the implementation of the budget and assessments in WP2, WP4 and WP6.

Most of the data are included in deliverable reports, whose classification is stated in the Grant Agreement. The treatment of data from reports and other materials falling outside this classification will be evaluated according to the exploitation plan (IPR) and ethical issues (protection of personal data) before making them public, but following the principles of “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”.

NPOWER is an open science project. Therefore, results will be made findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR). This will be applicable not only to scientific publications and public deliverables, but also to other research data and metadata. Due to the multidisciplinary character of NPOWER project, Zenodo is the most suitable public repository, for the storage of open access materials, as it provides both open access and persistent identifiers (DOI). Licensing will follow the requirements of the Grant Agreement in terms of reusability (CC-BY for results and CC0 for metadata).

During the project, the internal storage of different data is done in the general secured sharepoint in Microsoft Office 365 OneDrive administrated by CETENMA. In addition, each partner takes appropriate technical and organizational measures against accidental loss or destruction of project data.

NPOWER data management will follow ethical principles and regulations and consider the sensitive information, following the approach “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. Informed consent will be asked in NPOWER event to the participants.

More detailed information is provided in the deliverable of ethics (D8.2) and the dissemination, exploitation and communication plan (D7.2).

In conclusion, the D8.1 “Data Management Plan” provides the guidelines for the data management. This data management plan is a living document, which will be updated in M23 with deliverable D8.3 “Updated Data Management Plan I”.

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10. Annex

Informed consent template

Project acronym	NPower
Project full name	Balancing Nitrogen and Phosphorus flows by budgeting at Regional scale
Project partner	[Partner Acronym]
Project duration	January 2025-December 2028
Funding and grant agreement	Horizon Europe, GA, 101181873

INTRODUCTION

As part of NPower project, videos, audios and photographs may be recorded during the meetings and related activities such as workshops and events, aimed at project documentation, promotional activities and other related purposes.

The collected data will be used for research and project purposes only and always while protecting the identity of participants. Wherever possible, images or recordings will be anonymized or used in a way that does not disclose identifiable personal information unless explicit permission is provided

This documentation will be collected to document and promote the work carried out, showcasing the project's progress, share the results with the NPower community and promote sustainable management of N and P assets. The photos and videos may appear in reports, presentations, website, social media and other promotional materials, and educational resources.

The NPower project is committed to upholding the highest ethical standards in all activities, in particular: respect for autonomy, confidentiality, non-discrimination, transparency and data protection compliance.

USE OF IMAGES/RECORDINGS

I understand that the images/recordings may be used for project documentation, educational content, promotional activities, and other related purposes.

I agree that these images/recordings may be used without any further approval from me.

Duration of Consent

This consent is valid indefinitely for project-related activities unless revoked in writing.

Revocation will apply to future use of your images/recordings but cannot retroactively affect materials already published or disseminated.

No Compensation

I understand that I will not receive any monetary compensation for my participation or for the use of images/recordings.

Revocation of Consent

I understand that I may revoke this consent at any time by providing written notice to the Project Coordinator (Miguel Ángel Suárez, CETENMA, miguelangel.suarez@cetenma.es) or DPO (Aran Blanco, KVC, aran.blanco@kveloce.com).

Rights and Ownership

I understand that the NPower project and its affiliates will own the rights to these images/recordings and may use them in any lawful and project-related manner, such as in reports, educational resources, promotional materials, or social media posts

Voluntary Participation

My agreement to participate and allow photography/recording is completely voluntary, and I am free to withdraw my consent at any time.

Release of Liability

I release the NPower project, its coordinators, and affiliates from any claims, damages, or liability arising from the use of my image/voice/likeness

I, _____, hereby declare to be of legal age (over 18 years old) and agree to be photographed and/or recorded as part of the NPower project activities

Participant's Information:

Name: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

I have received a copy of this agreement. This consent form is made pursuant to the relevant national, European data protection laws and regulations and personal data treatment obligations.

PRIVACY NOTICE

1. [What do I need to know about the data compilation and how the information gathered is going to be managed?](#)

Personal information gathered for this study will be kept confidential in line with the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).

Data are being collected by the Consortium of Horizon Europe project NPOWER (Balancing Nitrogen and Phosphorus fLOWs by budgEting at Regional scale) under Grant Agreement 101181873 for the exclusive purpose of project implementation.

Any data bearing your name will be kept in a locked filing cabinet or in a computer pass-worded file. The results of your participation will be kept anonymous for the final outcome. Public results will contain information in the form of percentages, statistics and general information, no individual or personal information will be included.

Your detailed responses will be kept confidential, except within the Project Consortium, for which sharing the information is required to achieve the research targets. Only average figures will be made public in the public deliverables, open presentations, public reports and any other communication and dissemination actions aimed to external parties. Every effort will be made by the researcher to preserve your confidentiality including the following:

- Assigning code names/numbers for participants that will be used on all research notes and documents.

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- Keeping notes, interview transcriptions, and any other identifying participant information in a locked file cabinet in the personal possession of the researchers.

Your records will be kept confidential and will not be released without your consent except as required by law.

2. Which data will be collected?

The type of data that can be collected in the participation phase of the project include: IP address, mobile telephone number, email, personal identification data, organisation, work practices.

Some online meetings may be recorded. Participants will always be informed beforehand and given the opportunity to refuse consent.

3. More information about taking part.

You can stop being part of this pilot at any time, without giving any reason. If you want to withdraw, your information/data will also be withdrawn from the project, unless you consent to us retaining your data/information.

All partners taking part into the NPOWER project operate under the regulations of the GDPR. As such, if you have any concerns about your data, you have the right to request access to and rectification or erasure of personal data, and the right to request restriction of processing and portability of data.¹ For that purpose you may contact the persons below.

4. Contacts for further information

Project Coordinator
Miguel Ángel Suárez Valdés, CETENMA
miguelangel.suarez@cetenma.es

Host Regional Cluster
Insert name of Regional Cluster leader
Insert contact info of Regional Cluster leader

Data Protection Officer
Aran Blanco, KVELOCE
aran.blanco@kveloce.com

¹ You also have the right to lodge a complaint with a data supervisory authority. A full list of the country specific data supervisory authorities can be found at:

https://edpb.europa.eu/about-edpb/about-edpb/members_en#member-fi